

Shuang-zhu-zhan, a high quality rice variety planted widely in southern China.

Two semidwarf indica scented rice varieties were produced. Gan-wan-xian 22 was released for commercial production in Mar 1994 by the Seed Board of Jiangxi Province. It is the first modern scented variety in Jiangxi Province.

Gan-wan-xian 22 was derived from the cross IR841/84-06, a strain from the cross of IR24/Gui-chao. The selected strain SR4044 has aromatic grain, good grain appearance, intermediate amylose content (AC) and gelatinization temperature (GC), soft gel consistency (GC), and promising agronomic characteristics (see table). It yielded 5.3 t/ha in regional trials for the late rice crop in the double-cropped system in 1992-93 and was not significantly different from the high-yielding check M112. It yielded 15% more than Shuang-zhu-zhan. Its average yield was 4.5-6.8 t/ha. In Oct 1992, Jiangxi-xiang-si-miao rice, a commercial product of Gan-wan-xian 22, won a bronze prize at the First China Agriculture Exposition.

SR5041, another preferred scented rice variety was also put into production. It is from the cross of IR841/Zao-xiang 17, has a heavy fragrance, low AC value, low GT, and soft GC (see table). The average yield was about 4.1 t/ha, which

Quality characteristics of Gan-wan-xian 22, SR5041, and Shuang-zhu-zhan.^a

Characteristic	Gan-wan-xian 22	SR5041	Shuang-zhu-zhan
Milling quality			
Brown rice (%)	79.6	80.1	76.4
Milled rice recovery (%)	70.1	70.5	71.1
Head rice (%)	60.1	61.5	67.8
Grain appearance			
1,000-grain whole			
Milled rice weight (g)	18.4	20.2	12.1
Kernel length (mm)	6.9	7.2	5.8
L-W ratio	3.3	3.4	2.9
Chalky kernels (%)	14.0	9.0	9.0
Area with chalkiness (%)	1.9	1.5	1.3
Chemical characteristics			
AC value (%)	20.1	16.1	26.6
Alkali spreading value	4.1	7.0	6.0
GC value (mm)	83.0	66.0	29.0
Protein content of milled rice (%)	6.5	7.1	6.7
Eating quality			
Cooked rice elongation	1.6	1.7	1.2
Aroma	Medium	Strong	None
Taste	Good	Very good	Good

^aSamples were from late rice crop in the double-cropped system, late 1992.

was 10% more than that of Shuang-zhu-zhan.

Gan-wan-xian 22 has good resistance to blast and brown planthopper. It was cultivated as a late rice variety in Jiangxi Province in 1993 on about 10,000 ha.

SR5041, also a late rice, has a growth duration that is 10 d shorter than that of Gan-wan-xian 22, which is similar to that of Shuang-zhu-zhan. Both scented rices are very popular in the local markets and are being exported to Southeast Asia. ■

Stability of rice grain quality under different fertilizer levels

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We conducted this experiment to study how the levels of fertilizer affect the stability of rice grain quality. Six varieties were grown in the 1993 wet season in a stability model where three N levels (0, 40, and 80 kg/ha), two P levels (0 and 40 kg/ha), and two K

levels (0 and 30 kg/ha) were combined into 12 fertilizer levels. Rice was dehulled using a Satake rice husking machine (model THU-35A) and McGill polisher no. 3.

The percentages of brown rice, white rice, and broken rice in all varieties were unstable under different fertilizer levels, with S^2_{di} significant from zero (Table 1). The responses of milling quality to fertilizer levels did not follow the linear model, suggesting that milling quality was affected by many other factors in addition to fertilizer levels.

Table 1. Stability parameters for milling quality of some varieties.

Variety	Brown rice(%)			White rice (%)			Broken rice (%)		
	\bar{X}	bi	S^2_{di}	\bar{X}	bi	S^2_{di}	\bar{X}	bi	S^2_{di}
OM987-1	77.8	0.77	0.65	68.2	0.73	2.09	36.1	0.27	35.34
IR58082	76.8	3.63	5.19	66.8	2.36	9.46	33.8	0.17	16.10
MTL 105	78.5	-0.04	0.14	70.0	0.28	0.56	21.5	2.92	54.14
OM269	78.8	0.49	5.49	69.6	0.69	5.68	30.4	1.59	66.80
IR53964-39	77.9	0.91	0.76	68.3	0.87	2.69	23.3	1.43	40.67
IR29723	78.3	0.21	0.35	68.8	1.16	2.09	23.0	0.17	30.63

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Table 2. Stability parameters for grain dimensions and chemical properties of some varieties.

Variety	Grain length			(mm)Length-width ratio			Chalkiness (%)			Amylose content (%)		
	\bar{X}	bi	S ² di	\bar{X}	bi	S ² di	\bar{X}	bi	S ² di	\bar{X}	bi	S ² di
OM987-1	8.7	2.55	0.040	3.16	1.23	0.010	5	0.50	0.30	23.9	1.33	2.07
IR58082	7.8	0.15	0.050	3.01	0.83	0.007	5	1.35	0.20	24.3	0.54	4.41
MTL 105	7.7	0.51	0.001	2.66	1.76	0.010	1	1.06	0.08	26.3	0.90	2.75
OM269	8.5	1.17	0.040	3.41	0.70	0.005	1	0.62	0.05	26.4	1.43	2.45
IR53964-39	8.0	1.22	-0.0006	2.72	0.79	0.002	5	1.17	0.01	28.3	0.71	3.58
IR29723	8.0	0.46	-0.0006	2.88	0.68	0.016	5	1.39	0.40	28	1.18	3.45

Physical dimensions as well as chalkiness were very stable (Table 2), and responses of these varieties followed the linear model. For amylose content, however, responses were quite complex and considered unstable under different fertilizer levels.

The results indicated that milling quality and amylose content were unstable under different fertilizer dosages while grain dimensions and chalkiness were stable. ■

Pest resistance—diseases

Inheritance of resistance to rice tungro spherical virus in some rice cultivars

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Many rice cultivars serve as sources of resistance to rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV). RTSV resistance could be an important factor in controlling tungro disease because the vector, green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*, can transmit the rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) only when it has previ-

Reactions to RTSV of F₁ and F₃ progenies from crosses of 3 resistant rice cultivars with TN1 and crosses between resistant parents.

Cultivar/cross	Reaction ^a	F ₃ lines				χ^2	P
		Resistant	Segregating	Susceptible	Fit		
Utri Merah	R	-	-	-	-	-	-
Utri Rajapan	R	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pankhari 203	R	-	-	-	-	-	-
Taichung Native 1	S	-	-	-	-	-	-
Utri Merah/TN1 (F ₁)	S	62	66	13	7:8:1	2.279	0.25-0.50
TN1/Utri Rajapan (F ₁)	S	21	-	65 ^b	1:3	0.010	0.90-0.95
Pankhari 203/TN1 (F ₁)	M	41	71	40	1:2:1	0.671	0.70-0.8
Utri Rajapan/Utri Merah (F ₁)	R	118	0	0	-	-	-
Utri Rajapan/Pankhari 203 (F ₁)	R	167	0	0	-	-	-

^aR = resistant, M = moderately resistant, S = susceptible. ^bPooled segregating and susceptible reactions.

ously acquired RTSV. However, the genetics of resistance to RTSV infection in these cultivars is not fully understood.

We undertook this study to efficiently breed cultivars resistant to RTSV.

We studied RTSV-resistant cultivars Utri Merah (IRGC Acc. 16680), Utri Rajapan (Acc. 16684), and Pankhari 203 (Acc. 5999). The F₁ and F₃ progenies of crosses between resistant cultivars and Taichung Native 1 (TN1), a RTSV-susceptible cultivar, were tested to determine the mode of inheritance for resistance to RTSV infection. We also determined the allelic relationships of the resistance genes among the resistant cultivars.

Thirty seedlings in each F₃ line were tested for RTSV, except for the F₃ lines of Utri Merah/TN1, for which 60 seedlings were inoculated per line.

In the artificial inoculation, five 10-d-old seedlings were grown in a clay pot

Histogram of the infection rates with RTSV in the Utri Merah/TN1 F₃ lines.